

Dynamic control of weight-update linearity in magneto-ionic synapses

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Abstract

Multifunctional hardware technologies for neuromorphic computing are essential for replicating the complexity of biological neural systems, thereby improving the performance of artificial synapses and neurons. Integrating ionic and spintronic technologies offers new degrees of freedom to modulate synaptic potentiation and depression, introducing novel magnetic functionalities alongside the established ionic analogue behaviour. We demonstrate that magneto-ionic devices can perform as synaptic elements with dynamically tunable depression linearity controlled by an external magnetic field, a functionality reminiscent of neuromodulation in biological systems. By applying

magnetic fields we significantly reduce the non-linearity of synaptic depression, transitioning from an exponential dependence to a linear response at higher fields. Neural network simulations reveal that this magnetically-induced linearity enhancement improves learning accuracy across a wide range of learning rates, which is retained after the magnetic field is removed. These findings highlight the versatility and promise of magneto-ionic devices for developing tunable synaptic elements for neuromorphic hardware.

Keywords: Magneto-ionics, artificial synapses, nanodevices, weight-update linearity

Spintronics offers a rich and well-controlled platform for neuromorphic system design. Spin-torque nano-oscillators,¹⁻⁶ superparamagnetic magnetic tunnel junctions,⁷⁻¹¹ magnetic chiral structures,¹²⁻¹⁵ ferromagnetic/antiferromagnetic heterostructures^{16,17} and spin-waves^{18,19} have all been used in a variety of neuromorphic computing applications.

One key challenge in neuromorphic spintronics is the difficulty of implementing learning mechanisms using the traditionally binary memory functionality²⁰ that magnetic systems provide. Analogue memory alternatives have been demonstrated using magnetic domain wall motion, however, domain-wall based devices face important scalability challenges and have yet to achieve the level of technological development of its main competitor in neuromorphic hardware technologies: memristors.²¹⁻²⁷ Nevertheless, memristors, which are driven through ionic effects, also face significant challenges, particularly in achieving a linear weight-update behavior during learning. In most memristive devices, the conductance changes non-linearly with applied voltage pulses, which negatively impacts learning accuracy.²⁸⁻³⁰ Strategies to enhance linearity in memristors, such as doping active oxides³¹⁻³³ and using variable pulse amplitudes,²⁹ remain complex and are difficult to implement in large-scale hardware systems. Thus, there remains a significant need for a highly scalable memory technology that offers both reprogrammability and linear weight updates.

In this work, we address this challenge by combining the strengths of both spintronics and ionic effects into magneto-ionic devices, which have already shown great potential as analogue synaptic elements^{34–36} with a spin-dependent electrical read-out. Specifically, we introduce analogue spintronic synapses where the linearity of weight updates, defined by the number of gate pulses applied, can be dynamically tuned using an external magnetic field. The ability to dynamically control the linearity of weight updates through the application of a constant magnetic field relies on the competition between the gate-controlled magnetic anisotropy^{37–41} and the external magnetic field on the alignment of spins. Notably, we demonstrate that these magneto-ionic synapses exhibit improved learning accuracy when operating under a 41 mT magnetic field, with much of this performance retained even after the magnetic field is removed.

This level of tunability provides not only scalable devices with linear-weight updates, but also greater flexibility in mimicking synaptic behavior compared to conventional memristors. Dynamic tunability of the learning capabilities of a synapse mirrors the effects of neuromodulation in biological systems, where external stimuli modulate the learning capacity of neural circuits. This functionality is made possible in hardware by the key assembly of the analogue functionalities of ionic systems and the physics of spintronics devices in magneto-ionic systems, and can not be realised in neither ionic nor spintronics devices separately.

Magnetic memristive-like behaviour

The magneto-ionic devices consist of Hall crosses fabricated from CoFeB/HfO₂ bilayers, containing a gate electrode on top of the Hall cross (see supplementary information (SI), section 1). Fig. 1 (a) shows a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of a typical device. Fig. 1 (b) shows anomalous Hall effect (AHE) half-hysteresis loops obtained by ramping the magnetic field from positive to negative values, after application of gate voltage pulses (1 to 16) of -9 V and 750 ms. These curves show a progressive loss of remanence, indicating a weakening of the perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (PMA) component, linked to a gate-induced

Figure 1: **Magneto-ionic memristive-like behaviour.** (a) Graphic representation and SEM image of a magneto-ionic device. (b) Half-hysteresis loops for the device in the initial state (dark line) and the subsequent curves obtained after the application of subsequent pulses of $-9\ \text{V}$ and a duration of $750\ \text{ms}$. (inset) Progression for each subsequent pulse application from 1 to 16 between 0 and $20\ \text{mT}$. (c) AHE as a function of the gating time at a constant field of $5\ \text{mT}$, each point is recorded after the application of a gate voltage pulse of $-9\ \text{V}$ or $+9\ \text{V}$ for depression and potentiation, respectively.

oxidation of the Co and Fe atoms at the interface⁴²⁻⁴⁴ (see SI section 2). Fig. 1 (c) shows the memristive-like behaviour of the AHE signal, controlled by magneto-ionic gating at a constant magnetic field of 5 mT. The dark to bright colour progression indicates the effects of single gate voltage pulses alternating between amplitudes of -9 V and +9 V (750 ms pulse width, 5 s waiting time between pulses), showing the high degree of reversibility of the gate effects.

The analog change in the profile of the AHE signal as a function of the number of gate pulses sets the basis for the synaptic behaviour in these devices. Synaptic potentiation and depression are achieved by using positive and negative gate-voltage pulses, respectively. Other studies have shown the use of gate voltage pulses to achieve this functionality but only within the PMA window of operation of the device giving a total variation of about 50%.³⁴ Exploiting the full range of voltage-induced changes up to the spin reorientation transition allows for a wider amplitude of the signal between potentiation and depression leading, in the present case, to a total variation of about 100%, which gives the possibility of having a larger number of stable intermediate states to be used as synaptic weights. A key aspect of the design of synaptic elements with memristor-like devices is the ability to produce a number of analog states within the window of operation of the device, in order to provide a wide range of synaptic weight values. In the present case, this window of operation is given by the maximum and minimum values of the AHE signal, given by a dominant PMA state and a dominant in-plane anisotropy state (IPA), respectively.

Magnetic field control of synaptic linearity

As mentioned, the interest in the use of magneto-ionic synaptic elements is the possibility to exploit their magnetic degree of freedom to design new functionalities. Up to this point, the memristive-like behaviour of these devices was characterised using a 5 mT constant mag-

Figure 2: **Magnetic-field driven tunability of the weight-update linearity.** (a) Potentiation and depression behaviour conducted under different magnetic fields. (b) Hysteresis loops before and after full depression and their differences at the magnetic fields shown in (a). (c) Non-linearity factor in depression and in potentiation, as a function of the magnetic field

netic field, to avoid the loss of AHE signal when going from IPA back to PMA due to the formation of a multidomain pattern (see SI section 6). However, operation under magnetic field can be used to significantly act on the depression behaviour. Fig. 2 (a) shows depression/potentiation cycles obtained at magnetic fields between 5 mT and 78 mT, where the amplitude of the signal as well as the dependence of the anomalous Hall resistance on the number of pulses is progressively modified. Fig. 2 (b) shows the hysteresis loops obtained before and after full depression, and the vertical lines show the position of the different magnetic fields under which the plots in (a) were measured. For each vertical line, the signal range between the two hysteresis loops determines the amplitude of the depression/potentiation cycles. This difference becomes progressively smaller at high magnetic fields, which explains the decrease in amplitude of the depression/potentiation cycles. The cycles measured under relatively low fields have a profile that is very sensitive to the gate-induced variation in the direction of the easy axis, as the anomalous Hall resistance depends on the projection of

the magnetisation vector in the out-of-plane direction. In contrast, in the limit of relatively high fields (above 100 mT), the difference between the two hysteresis loops disappears, even when the oxidation and reduction process induced by ionic gating continues to take place, uninfluenced by the magnitude of the applied magnetic field. This is due to the fact that at sufficiently high fields, the signature of the gate-induced changes in anisotropy is largely suppressed in AHE measurements, as the magnetic field takes over as the dominant energy term and all spins align along the direction of the out-of-plane applied magnetic field, regardless of the gate-driven changes in the PMA component. In between these two regimes, a mixture of both effects is at play, which introduces a progression from a highly non-linear depression profile towards a significantly more linear behaviour as the magnetic field increases (see SI section 4). A non-linearity factor has been calculated as a function of the magnetic field and is presented in Fig. 2 (c). This factor is defined as $\Delta AHE_{1/2}/\Delta AHE_F$, where ΔAHE_F is the full amplitude of the AHE resistance in depression (between 1 and 27 pulses) and $\Delta AHE_{1/2}$ is the AHE resistance amplitude in the middle of the depression process (at 14 pulses).⁴⁵ For a linear response, the non-linearity factor gives a value of 0.5, and progressively increases/decreases when non-linearity is present. The progression from a non-linear depression behaviour towards a linear process is clearly visible in the values of the non-linearity factor, which rapidly approach 0.5 as the magnetic field increases. On the other hand, this effect is highly suppressed in potentiation, which is linked to a difference in the dependence of the PMA component on the number of gate-voltage pulses applied (see SI section 4) as positive and negative gate voltages drive two distinct chemical processes, oxidation and reduction, which can have different dynamics.

It is important to verify that each individual intermediate state of the synaptic element will not overlap with other neighbouring states due to an eventual time evolution occurring right after the pulse has been applied. Fig. 3 (a) shows the relaxation of each of the intermediate states over the course of 1.5 hours, where two important observations can be made:

Figure 3: **Stability of intermediate magneto-ionic states.** (a) Intermediate magneto-ionic states in depression and potentiation obtained through the application of gate-voltage pulses of a duration of 750 ms and amplitudes of -9 V and +9 V, respectively. (inset) Detailed view of the AHE fast relaxation after the gate pulse used to set state 2. (b) Detailed view of the time evolution of intermediate states 2 and 6, in depression and potentiation, respectively.

(I) a significant relaxation takes place shortly after the gate voltage pulse has been applied, and (II) a clear difference can be seen in the magneto-ionic relaxation dynamics between depression and potentiation. A detailed view of intermediate states 2 and 6, in depression and potentiation, respectively, is presented in Fig. 3 (b). It is also observed that the relaxation can be divided in two relatively slow and fast parts. The fast relaxation takes place right after the end of the voltage pulse, which is seen as a sharp spike in the AHE signal, as highlighted by green lines in Fig. 3 (a) and in the inset, showing the fast relaxation after the gate pulse used to set state 2. The time difference between the tip of the spike and the beginning of the slow relaxation process is 5 seconds. Consequently, all the AHE data points presented in Fig. 1 (c) were recorded 5 s after the application of the gate pulses, to avoid the AHE spike. This part of the relaxation is attributed to interface charge accumulation effects on the magnetic anisotropy, which are volatile and can also significantly modify the magnetic anisotropy in PMA materials.^{46–48} The subsequent slow relaxation, is therefore attributed to ionic effects, and is highly asymmetric for positive and negative applied gate voltages.

Unlike memristors, where voltage-controlled ionics induces analog changes in conductivity through the formation of conductive filaments inside an oxide, magneto-ionic devices rely on oxidation/reduction at the oxide/ferromagnetic interface to achieve non-volatile changes in the magnetic anisotropy. This makes the process of potentiation and depression fundamentally asymmetric, as depression is linked to metallic oxidation, and potentiation to the reduction of the metal's oxide. X-ray absorption spectroscopy scans of an as-grown sample, and samples exposed to negative gate voltages using ionic liquid gating show that the loss of PMA under negative gate voltages is linked to oxidation of Fe and Co atoms (see SI section 2). This leads to the need for a voltage-induced reduction to recover the initial state. As the oxides of Co and Fe are more thermodynamically stable than their metallic counterparts in ambient conditions, the system can show a tendency to spontaneously re-oxidise at room temperature in the presence of oxygen and water from the atmosphere. This makes the ionic processes happening at negative and positive gate voltages of the same amplitude highly asymmetric, where spontaneous re-oxidation, that is the recovery after the reduction obtained through the application of a positive gate voltage, can lead to larger changes and ionic dynamics that extend over longer periods of time with respect to the voltage-induced oxidation process. Therefore, the oxidation-driven depression regime of the magneto-ionic synaptic elements seems to be the one that is more adapted for long-term retention of the synaptic states.

Artificial neural network simulations with magneto-ionic synapses

The concept of dynamically tunable weight-update linearity was explored by conducting simulations of an artificial neural network trained using the MNIST dataset and using synaptic elements including the physics of the magneto-ionic devices. The simulated artificial neural network contains a hidden layer of 512 neurons and a total of 529,408 synapses, a graphic representation is presented in Fig. 4 (a). The MNIST baseline shown in Fig.4 (b) is the max-

Figure 4: **Artificial neural network with magneto-ionic synapses in a learning scenario.** (a) Proposed hardware implementation of a two-device based artificial magneto-ionic synapse. A cartoon of the three-layer neural network used in the simulations is also depicted in (a). (b) Testing accuracy on the MNIST dataset as a function of the learning rate in simulations considering the behaviour of magneto-ionic devices under 5 mT and 41 mT, with the larger bands corresponding to the standard deviation. The accuracy of the training done at 41 mT is also evaluated when the field is reduced to 5 mT after training.

imum accuracy obtained considering artificial synapses with an ideal linear and symmetric behaviour of the weight evolution as a function of the number of weight updates in potentiation and depression. The MNIST baseline is therefore the highest accuracy that an artificial network of this size can produce and it is used as a reference to compare the performance of simulations based on the experimentally obtained behaviour of magneto-ionic devices. In order to implement a magneto-ionic artificial synapse allowing a stable and tunable weight-update linearity in potentiation and depression, as well as positive and negative values of the weights, a two-device design of the synapse is proposed as shown in Fig. 4 (a). The value of each weight is calculated by subtracting the values of the Hall resistance in depression of two different devices, using the data presented in Fig. 2 (a). In hardware, this design could

be implemented by recording the sum of the Hall voltages of two crosses connected through the Hall voltage leads, and by running bias currents with opposite signs in the two Hall crosses as shown in Fig.4 (a). This design relies solely on the oxidation-driven part of the weight-update profile, which shows the highest stability of the intermediate magneto-ionic states, and is also the part most susceptible to the magnetic-field control of linearity. Given the magneto-ionic characteristics of the synapses within this model, it is possible that either of the devices reaches a saturation point of full oxidation, where weights can not be increased any further. In hardware, this can be solved by resetting both devices to their initial fully reduced states, using a positive gate voltage, and subsequently applying a negative voltage to one device to reinstate the last weight value (see SI section 7.1). Therefore, this design allows to fully recreate a synaptic element that under a magnetic field of 41 mT, could perform a linear weight update in both depression and potentiation.

The results of the training using data of the magneto-ionic devices measured under 5 mT and 41 mT are presented in Fig. 4 (b). The training done under 41 mT as a function of learning rate shows initially an increase in accuracy at learning rates between 500 and 1000 with respect to the training done under 5 mT, this is attributed to the higher precision of the weight update in the linear dependence, against the non-linear dependence for 41 mT and 5 mT, respectively. At higher learning rates, increasing the magnetic field leads to a dramatic increase in accuracy, where the improvement can be of about 6% due to a rapid decrease in accuracy for the non-linear weight-update profile that is used in the training under 5 mT. In addition, a network trained under a magnetic field of 41 mT retains a relatively high accuracy when the field is decreased to 5 mT at the end of the training process, compared to the results where the training is made entirely under a field of 5 mT. This shows the importance of conducting training with hardware that allows for a linear weight-update, while going back to a non-linear dependence for inference does not critically degrade the accuracy.

In conclusion, magneto-ionic devices can perform as synaptic elements where the linear-

ity of the weight-update behaviour can be dynamically controlled using a magnetic field, a functionality that is inherent to the magnetic nature of the devices. Using this functionality, simulations of a learning process using a two-device synapse design show that using high magnetic fields during training can significantly increase the learning accuracy, and that this improvement can still be significant after the magnetic field is reduced after training. This functionality opens new perspectives for the use of the magnetic degree of freedom of synaptic elements bringing together magnetism and ionics. One interesting perspective of these results is the implementation of bioinspired functionalities such as the effects of neuromodulators. A global effect on the activity of neural circuits in the brain, such as the activation or silencing of synapses, can be influenced by the location and temporal dynamics of neuromodulator release.⁴⁹ In a magneto-ionic synaptic array, a local magnetic field applied through patterned micro-coils or strip lines could induce the preferential use of a group of synapses for learning a specific task, introducing control over the topology of the learning process on a chip. The recent developments in magneto-ionics also give an outlook into a possible enhancement of device capabilities such as the increase in the signal amplitude by integration of magnetic tunnel junctions for read-out, and the implementation of a magnetic-field control of weight-update linearity at the single device level through the magneto-ionic modulation of exchange bias.^{50–54} In terms of operation speed, we show that higher amplitudes of the gate voltage allow for the use of shorter pulse widths (see SI section 7.3), therefore further miniaturisation of the gated area and optimisation of the oxide gate materials and thickness could bring significant improvements in speed. In addition, other magneto-ionic systems relying on the dynamics of mobile H^+ or Li^+ ^{55,56} ions have shown dynamics down into the sub-ms range, which offers excellent perspectives for further improvement of the design of magneto-ionic synaptic elements.

Supplementary information

XAS measurements in as-grown and gated samples, modeling of the gate-controlled linearity of synaptic depression, two-point resistance measurements under gating, AHE evolution under gating and zero magnetic field. Details about the incorporation of device physics into artificial neural network simulations: weight behaviour, pulse length threshold, reading noise, device variability and the simulation implementation details.

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Figure 5: For Table of Contents Only

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Dynamic control of weight-update linearity in magneto-ionic synapses

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1 Device fabrication

The magneto-ionic devices used in this study are fabricated from Ta(5 nm)/Co₂₀Fe₆₀B₂₀ (1 nm)/HfO₂(3 nm) multilayers grown by magnetron sputtering deposition. 300 nm wide Hall bar devices were fabricated using e-beam lithography. Subsequently, a layer of HfO₂(20 nm) grown by atomic layer deposition at a temperature of 100 °C was incorporated, and finally

a gate electrode of ITO (Indium Tin Oxide, 100 nm) was patterned on top of the Hall cross.

2 X-ray absorption spectroscopy

X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) was measured at the SEXTANTS beamline (SOLEIL).^{1,2} The samples were mounted on copper sample holders using carbon tape and introduced under vacuum in the MAGELEC sample environment. The XAS spectra were collected in Total Electron Yield (TEY) mode via a Keithley picoammeter, employing an energy resolution of about 400meV.

XAS measurements are most sensitive to elements near the surface of the sample, making it difficult to observe the iron and cobalt edges if a thick layer of HfO₂ and ITO are present, as it is the case in the devices presented in the main article (20 nm and 50 nm, respectively). Therefore, we used the multilayer structure of Ta(5nm)/CoFeB (1nm)/HfO₂(3 nm) used to fabricate the devices presented in the main article and placed instead of the solid-state gate, an ionic liquid gate ([EMI] [TFSI])^{3,4} and applied a gate voltage using a glass plate coated with ITO as a top electrode. After the voltage application, the glass plate and ionic liquid were removed to perform the XAS measurements, as the effects of magneto-ionic gating are non-volatile. Consequently, the voltages used for solid-state devices in the manuscript cannot be directly compared to those used with the ionic liquid setup, we have used as guide the hysteresis loops obtained after ionic liquid gating to create states that have dominant PMA and in-plane anisotropy.

Fig.S1 (a) shows the hysteresis loop of the as-grown Ta(5nm)/CoFeB (1nm)/HfO₂(3 nm) multilayer, while (b) and (c) show the signal after gating under -2 V for 6 min and -3.3 V for 1 hour, respectively. In (a), the signal shows that the sample has perpendicular magnetic

Figure S1: Anomalous Hall effect loops of the as-grown sample (a) and samples gated using gate voltages of -2 V for 6 min (b) and -3.3 V for 1 hour (c).

anisotropy, while its loss due to gating under negative voltages is seen for both (b) and (c). As expected, the application of a negative gate voltage in the same configuration as in the devices in the main text (CoFeB grounded, gate voltage applied to the top ITO electrode) induces a weakening of the perpendicular magnetic anisotropy in the sample. It is important to mention that the three measurements presented in Fig. S1 have been conducted using four contacts placed manually on the sample surface through wire bonding. This means that the areas probed are not of the same size, and that, in turn, the intensities of the AHE voltages cannot be compared between different samples. Fig.S2 shows the corresponding XAS spectra for the samples presented in Fig.S1 (and an additional sample exposed to a gate voltage of -2 V for 1 min), where a clear signature of oxidation in both the Co and Fe signals can be observed under gating. For comparison, reference samples of metallic Fe and Co have also been measured, and resemble the profile obtained for the as-grown sample.

In the Fe edge, for relatively soft gating conditions (-2 V for 1 min and 6 min) the XAS profile does not change strongly, however, a clear increase in the relative intensity of the L_3 edge is observed upon gating with negative voltages. This is shown in a rescaled view of the XAS profiles in Fig.S2 (b) for the samples gated using a gate voltage of -2 V. A similar signature of gentle oxidation has already been reported in the XAS signal of ionic liquid gated Pt/Co/HfO₂ films,⁵ which in the present case could be related to an increase of the content

Figure S2: XAS measurements in the Fe and Co edges before and after gating. (a) and (b) show the evolution of the signal from a reference Fe sample, an as-grown sample and gated samples obtained using different gating parameters: -2 V for 1 min and 6 min, as well as -3.3 V for 1 hour. Measurements of the Co edge for all samples are presented in (c) and (d).

of Fe^{2+} in the gated samples. However, when a more aggressive gating protocol is used, namely the application of a gate voltage of -3.3 V for 1 hour, the profile of the absorption signal changes drastically, as shown in Fig. S2 (a), giving rise to two distinct peaks, that can be related to the dominant presence of Fe^{3+} .⁶⁻⁸

Interestingly, the appearance of two very different oxidation states obtained using -2 V for 6 min and -3.3 V for 1 hour, can not be clearly evaluated from the AHE measurements, that only show the overall loss of PMA in both cases. This is therefore a key aspect that plays a role for reversibility, since more gentle gating protocols produce reversible magneto-ionic effects as shown in the main text and previously by ionic liquid gating in the same multilayers,³ while the strong oxidation obtained after gating with a voltage of -3.3 V for 1 hour is irreversible for gate voltages up to +4 V.

The XAS profile of the Co edge is also presented in Fig.S2 (c) and (d), where a similar change in intensity of the L_3 edge as that observed in the Fe edge is seen between the as-grown sample and the sample gated using -2 V for 1 min. For longer gating times, the signal becomes relatively weak, limiting the conclusions that can be drawn. This may be due to the fact that the Co concentration in the multilayers used is three times smaller than that of Fe ($\text{Co}_{20}\text{Fe}_{60}\text{B}_{20}$), and therefore the noise could increase more rapidly for oxidised samples. In previous studies we have shown the equivalence between ionic liquid gating and solid state gating, and that their combination is of great value to produce both an evaluation of the device performance and an in-depth analysis of the magneto-ionic mechanisms at play⁴. In the present case, the XAS measurements in samples after ionic liquid gating confirm that the weakening of the PMA that is observed in devices under negative gate voltages is linked to an gate-driven oxidation process, and that reversing this effect implies a reduction process under positive gate voltage.

Figure S3: Hysteresis cycle of Hall voltage before and after removing the voltage offset.

3 Hall voltage measurements

The transverse Hall voltage measured with the two leads of the Hall cross also includes a component of the longitudinal resistance. This occurs due to the electrical misalignment of the leads, resulting in an offset in the hysteresis cycle, as illustrated in Fig. S3. To ensure consistent comparison of results between different devices, we subtract this offset when presenting the data.

4 Modeling gate-controlled linearity and asymmetry in potentiation/depression

The changes in linearity are related to a competition between the gate-induced variations in the strength of the out of plane magnetic anisotropy component, inducing spins to rotate towards (away from) the in-plane direction during depression (potentiation), and the external

magnetic field applied, which forces spins to align in the perpendicular direction. To better describe this key aspect, we have modeled the behaviour of a macrospin ensemble using the Stoner-Wohlfarth model. In this description, the total energy of the system can be described as follows:

$$E \propto \frac{K_u}{M_s} \sin^2(\theta) + \frac{K_i}{M_s} \cos^2(\theta) - \mu_0 H \cos(\theta) \quad (\text{S1})$$

Where $\frac{K_u}{M_s}$ and $\frac{K_i}{M_s}$ are the anisotropy constant to saturation magnetisation ratios for two perpendicular and in-plane (with respect to the sample surface) components of the magnetic anisotropy, μ_0 is the vacuum permeability, H is the magnetic field. The angle θ is the angle between the magnetisation and the magnetic field and also the angle between the magnetisation and the perpendicular anisotropy easy axis, as the magnetic field is applied in the perpendicular direction. The first term introduces energy minima in the perpendicular direction of magnetization, while the second one introduces minima in one direction in the plane of the sample, which is an approximation to the competition between perpendicular magnetic anisotropy, and the easy anisotropy plane in the plane of the sample that is linked to shape anisotropy in ultra-thin films. The third term corresponds to the Zeeman energy, which varies with the magnitude of the magnetic field.

We have arbitrarily fixed the value of $\frac{K_i}{M_s}$ to 0.2, and varied $\frac{K_u}{M_s}$ from 0.3 to 0, which results in a spin reorientation transition from PMA to IP anisotropy that can describe the effects of the application of a negative gate voltage. Within this model, the saturation magnetization is considered to have a constant value of 1. For each value of $\frac{K_u}{M_s}$, the total energy was calculated for five different values of H going from 0.05 to 0.25 in steps of 0.05. For each combination of $\frac{K_u}{M_s}$ and H the total energy was minimised with respect to θ to obtain the angle of minimum energy θ_{min} . This allowed us to track the variations in the alignment of the magnetisation vector with the perpendicular axis throughout the changes in the strength of the perpendicular anisotropy component and the magnetic field.

Using this simple model we were able to reconstruct the AHE signal, as it is proportional

Figure S4: Model of the evolution of the AHE signal as a function of the number of gate voltage pulses for five different magnetic fields (bottom panels, the magnetic field increases from violet to yellow). The curves on the left were modeled using the linear dependence of the magnetic anisotropy constant on the number of gate voltage pulses that is shown on the top panel. Non-linear dependences were used for the curves plotted on the center and right.

to the projection of the magnetisation on the perpendicular direction, that is, $M_s \cos(\theta_{\min})$. The modeled AHE signal as a function of the number of pulses was obtained considering a linear variation of the magnetic anisotropy with the number of gate pulses, as well as two other scenarios with highly non-linear variations as shown in Fig.S4. The top panels indicate the anisotropy variations used to simulate the AHE signals shown in the lower panels. We observe that higher magnetic fields induce a reduction in the non-linearity of the AHE profile, which is in good agreement with the experimental results presented in the main article. This simple model confirms that the linearity modulation observed is indeed related to the competition between the anisotropy components in the system and the magnetic field. Moreover, we show in the central and right panels in Fig. S4 that using a non-linear profile of the anisotropy vs. the number of pulses can significantly suppress the ability to use a magnetic field to control the linearity of the dependence of the AHE signal

on the number of gate voltage pulses. This has a direct connection to the differences in the gating effects observed in potentiation and depression. As mentioned in the main article, the same magnitude of the gate voltage is applied in depression and potentiation, -9 V and +9 V respectively. These two processes are highly asymmetric in their dynamics, as they are linked to oxidation and reduction, therefore, the variations of the perpendicular component of the magnetisation with the number of pulses is expected to be different for depression and potentiation. This leads to the conclusion that the suppressed control of linearity observed in potentiation may be linked to a different evolution of the component of perpendicular magnetic anisotropy compared to the depression process, driven by the difference in ionic dynamics in depression and potentiation under an applied gate voltage of the same absolute magnitude.

5 Sample 2-point resistance

We have evaluated the potential impact of ionic migration on the conductive properties of the magnetic layers. This was conducted by applying gate voltage pulses of -9 V with a pulse width of 750 ms to the sample and measuring successively the Hall resistance and the 2-point voltage as shown Fig. S5. The Hall resistance decreases significantly, as expected, while the 2-point voltage measurement shows only a decrease corresponding to 0.05% change in resistance. Full reduction is achieved at the end of the the measurement by applying a gate voltage of +11 V for 60 s. As expected, the Hall resistance returns to its initial value. Similarly, the 2-point recovers its initial value.

Figure S5: AHE and 2-point resistance evolution under gate voltage pulses of -9 V and 750 ms. A gate voltage of +11 V is applied for 60 s to recover the initial state.

6 Demagnetisation domain pattern formation under magneto-ionic gating

In order to investigate the formation of magnetic domains under gating in our devices, we have followed the AHE voltage between a fully saturated PMA state through the complete loss of PMA under negative voltages (-7 V) and its recovery under positive gate voltages (+9 V) under zero magnetic field applied, as shown in Fig.S6. The loss of PMA is accompanied by the loss of AHE resistance and the recovery of PMA under zero magnetic field applied gives a significantly reduced value of the AHE resistance, around zero, compared to the initial saturated state which is the signature of the formation of a demagnetization multidomain pattern. The fluctuations observed in AHE in the multidomain state are attributed to thermally activated domain wall hopping, which are more visible in nanometer-sized devices compared to larger devices. Further confirmation is obtained by the recovery of the initial

Figure S6: AHE resistance evolution going from a saturated PMA state, into an IP state (-7 V) and back to a PMA state (+9 V) with no external magnetic field applied. A 9 mT magnetic field was applied for 1 s at the end to saturate the magnetic state of the device.

AHE value by applying a magnetic field of 9 mT in the perpendicular direction, which indicates that the demagnetizing domain pattern is eliminated in favour of a saturated state along the direction of the magnetic field.

These measurements confirm the existence of magnetic domains in our magneto-ionic nanodevices, and that a coherent rotation of spins can be expected when a magnetic field is applied, however, in its absence, domain nucleation and expansion dynamics are at play. The existence of a demagnetization domain pattern after recovery of PMA is the reason why the devices are not operated at zero magnetic field in the present study, a minimum field of 5 mT is needed to obtain a saturated magnetic state when going from negative to positive gate voltages.

7 Artificial Neural Network Simulations

7.1 Weight Behaviour

As mentioned in the main article, to mitigate retention issues related to re-oxidation and fully exploit the linear weight-update obtained under magnetic field application, a dual-device scheme was employed to represent a single weight. In this design, the synaptic weight is determined by the subtraction of the Hall voltages of two independent Hall crosses. In this approach, only the oxidation process is utilized: a negative voltage pulse is applied to the first device to decrease the weight value and to the second device to increase the weight value as shown Fig. S8.

In this configuration, the devices require resetting when one reaches the minimum Hall resistance to allow the learning process to proceed. The reset is accomplished by transitioning the devices to an out-of-plane state via a positive voltage, followed by setting the weight difference with a negative voltage, as depicted in Fig. S7a. This full reduction process ensures the stability of subsequent learning states.

For the simulation, the Hall voltage curve during oxidation at 5 mT and 41 mT was fitted with exponential and linear curves, respectively. The fitted functions were used in the simulation without the need of any additional processing such as normalization. These fits, shown in Fig. S7b, closely match the data and are both invertible. Invertible functions are essential for simulating the behavior of individual weights. The inverse function allows to map a weight to a pulse number. The weight update is performed by incrementing this pulse number and then computing back a new weight value.

7.2 Pulse Length Threshold

The dynamics of ion species within the devices are constrained by a time constant; pulses that are too brief will not mobilize the oxygen species, resulting in no change in the Hall

Figure S7: a) Protocol used for resetting the weights once one of the two weights has reached the lowest value allowed. b) Hall resistance evolution measurement shown Figure 2a of the main text with an exponential (continuous red line) and linear (black) fit used for the simulation.

Figure S8: Protocol used for changing the weight value with two devices, a negative pulse is sent to the first device to decrease the weight a) or to the second device to increase it b).

voltage. This limitation must be considered in artificial neural networks, as minimal updates may not produce any physical effect. To ascertain the pulse length threshold, we measured the response to a cumulative gating duration of 5 seconds across different pulse lengths (e.g., 1 x 5 s, 5 x 1 s, 10 x 500 ms, etc.). The results at -9 V, shown in Fig. S9a, indicate that below 500 ms, the voltage change begins to diminish. Measurements conducted at -10 V reveal faster dynamics, with 125 ms pulses having roughly the same impact on the system’s ionics as longer pulses. Although higher voltages increase the risk of gate damage, the data suggests that with careful material and oxide engineering, dynamic performance can be considerably enhanced.

It is important to take these dynamics into account in the simulation, as during training, neural networks can rely on very small updates to reach an optimum value. Those updates may not be feasible physically because of the ions dynamics. To incorporate this effect into the simulation, we have prevented the system from implementing updates of less than a threshold value $\tau_{Threshold}$, as illustrated in Fig. S9b. Since there is a significant change between 125 ms and 62.5 ms at -10 V, we arbitrary choose $\tau_{Threshold} = 75$ ms for the simulation.

This cutoff significantly affects the system’s learning capabilities, as demonstrated in Fig. S10, where accuracies for various threshold values are plotted. The threshold substantially impacts small learning rates, rendering most updates ineffective. The 5 mT model, characterized by a decaying exponential, performs better at low learning rates when there is no threshold (resembling a linear curve for sufficiently small gradients). Consequently, the pulse length threshold most significantly affects 5 mT values, underscoring the importance of conducting network learning at higher fields like 41 mT.

7.3 Reading Noise

Reading noise was added during the forward pass and gradient computation. The noise was estimated by using the temporal evolution data of an intermediate state 5 min after the

Figure S9: a) Change in Hall voltage for 5 s of gating for different pulse lengths and different gate voltages. Shorter pulses only have a small effect on the Hall voltage. b) Simple model chosen to take into account the lack of effect of short pulses. Under a threshold, the weight is not updated. c) Accuracies of the ANN for different thresholds. When increasing the threshold, the best accuracy is obtained by increasing the learning rate.

Figure S10: Accuracies of the ANN for different thresholds. When increasing the threshold, the best accuracy is obtained by increasing the learning rate.

pulse.

7.4 Device variability

The measurements shown in this study come from several devices, all showing similar behaviour. However, some variations from device to device were observed, especially the Hall voltage response to the gate voltage pulses which was sometimes slightly faster or slower. This variability can affect the ANN performance so, to take this effect into account, we introduce a coefficient, $\alpha_{\text{variability}}$, for each device. These coefficients are initially randomized according to a normal distribution, $N(1, 0.2)$, and remain constant thereafter. For instance, a coefficient of $\alpha_{\text{variability}} = 1.1$ implies that a gate pulse with a duration of 1 second will have the effect of a pulse of 1.1 second on the Hall resistance. The normal distribution corresponds to the variation observed during experiments.

7.5 Implementation details

A Multi-Layer Perceptron with one hidden layer of 512 Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) and Batch Normalization without trainable parameters was trained using the dual-device scheme by computing the gradient of the Cross Entropy loss function. For all simulations, 20 epochs were performed on the MNIST dataset using a batch size of 128 images. Initialization of the weights was done by offsetting one of the devices such that the difference between devices is a uniform distribution $U(-0.01, 0.01)$. The input images had pixel values normalized between 0 and 1. These values were then converted to a current where a value of 1 corresponds to $I_{\text{inputscale}} = 1 \text{ mA}$. This current bias served as the synapse input, with the output being the measured Hall voltage. Each device represents a parameter requiring a gradient to be properly updated. The computation was done using PyTorch auto differentiation engine⁹ with a custom autograd function, which was designed to compute appropriately the gradients of each individual device, as well as to add noise during both the forward and the backward pass. A custom optimizer was devised to recover the value of the Hall resistance according to

a pulse number (which is equivalent to a gating time), hence the need for the field functions to be invertible mappings. The update of parameter is performed as follows. Let w_1 and w_2 be the parameters representing the two devices, w the actual weight used in the neural network and f_1, f_2 the field functions with invertible mappings f_1^{-1}, f_2^{-1} , α the learning rate and $\nabla_{w_1}\mathcal{L}(w), \nabla_{w_2}\mathcal{L}(w)$ the gradient of the loss function with respect to the parameters w_1 and w_2 respectively.

$$w_1 \leftarrow \begin{cases} f_1(f_1^{-1}(w_1) + \alpha|\nabla_{w_1}\mathcal{L}(w)|) & \text{if } \nabla_{w_1}\mathcal{L}(w) \geq 0 \\ w_1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$w_2 \leftarrow \begin{cases} f_2(f_2^{-1}(w_2) + \alpha|\nabla_{w_2}\mathcal{L}(w)|) & \text{if } \nabla_{w_2}\mathcal{L}(w) \geq 0 \\ w_2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

In this way, each device corresponds to either the positive or the negative part of the gradient such that we always increase the number of pulses on the field functions. When the full range of a device is consumed, i.e. that we arrive to a pulse number of 27 (or 20.25 s of gating time), we reset the other device to a pulse number of 0, and we update the current device to the same relative number of pulses to maintain the value for w .

To take into account the pulse length threshold, we only apply the update if $\alpha|\nabla_{w_{1/2}}\mathcal{L}(w)| > \tau_{Threshold}$. To take into account the device variability, we add the term $\alpha_{Variability}$ and the update becomes $\alpha\alpha_{Variability}|\nabla_{w_{1/2}}\mathcal{L}(w)|$. When changing the field from 41 mT to 5 mT after training, the inverse function for 41 mT is used to retrieve the pulse number for each individual weight and is converted to the new weight with the function for 5 mT. As a result, the difference of two devices representing a weight increases so we also increase the scaling of the input to mitigate this effect: $I_{inputscale} = \frac{A_{5\text{ mT}}}{A_{41\text{ mT}}} \times 1\text{ mA}$ where $A_{5\text{ mT}}, A_{41\text{ mT}}$ are the amplitude of the Hall resistance change after gating for the two magnetic fields. The test accuracy is then calculated on this new network.

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